

Humanity Is Tackling The New Variables To Live Sustainably

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Looking back at human history, our relationship with soil has influenced success of civilizations, and this may apply to climate change. While agriculture supported dense populations, more success helped people became free to pursue interests other than worrying what they were going to eat (1). Today, climate change is rearranging the equation as we started to look for ways to deal with the causes and effects to sustain civilizations. For example, in the past two decades, many countries and corporations took initiatives to set targets for emissions and water management. A recent breakthrough was Nuclear Fusion that can lead to limitless clean energy. Several satellite missions (7) were launched to survey earth water and to predict climate change events. Meanwhile, Environmental Justice is helping to use NASA data to assess the vulnerability and exposure of communities to environmental challenges.

I wrote the above paragraph after I recently received an invitation from LinkedIn editor to comment on a post related to battling the heat caused by climate change. I thought to elaborate on few points and publish this as a paper.

Since I mentioned that climate change is rearranging the equation, let's turn parts of the paragraph as a mathematical equation, to make some conclusions. We will assume we have the variables that are actions, results, causes, and effects. We may have these two equations:

- A. *Agriculture success influence (AS) = Supported dense population (SDP)***
- B. *More success in agriculture (MAS) = Supported dense population (SDP) + people became free to pursue other interests (POI)***

As climate change became a new variable in the past few decades, we can refer to climate change as (CLC). Climate change is mainly caused by atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases that produce a warming effect. Climate change, including increased heat (9), extended drought, and thirsty atmosphere has been linked to increased risk of wildfires (2). As the world population is increasing, the risk of wildfire and inability to feed the increasing population becoming higher (3). We will refer to the risks of wildfires and as (WFIRISK), and to the risk of inability to feed the increasing population as (FEEDRISK). Increased heat also causes more evaporation which in turn causes more precipitation and severe floods (8). We will refer to floods risks as (FLDRSKS). There are other cascading effects due to climate change, to mention few, heat mortality, impacts on ice sheets (6), rising water level, migration (4), and ecosystem effects such as invasive species, and habitat loss (5). Since climate change consequences have costs associated with reacting to it, we will refer to them as (CLCST).

As a result, the B equation could be rewritten as follows:

$$\mathbf{MAS - WFIRISK - FLDRSKS = (SDP + POI) - FEEDRISK - CLCST}$$

This is just a simplification of the part of the new challenges that humanity is facing due to climate change using a simple math equation. Thankfully, with technology advancements, innovations, and ability to share and replicate success quickly, humanity is on the road to reduce the impacts of climate change.

References

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